

EFFECT OF MARINE ENVIRONMENT ON THE INTERLAMINAR SHEAR STRENGTH OF GFRP COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Composite materials have been widely used to replace traditional materials because of their excellent properties. GFRP composites have good corrosion resistance and have good response to the effects of many chemical and water-related factors, making them suitable for use in harsh environments. These advantages have been explored by the oil and gas industry, where materials are often exposed to high relative humidity and saline atmosphere. However, it is essential to understand the effects of these scenarios on degradation of GFRP materials in order to extend their use. In order to understand the degradation of GFRP materials subjected to marine environment, the purpose of this paper is to study the aging of GFRP materials under hygrothermal ambient. Accelerated aging test were conducted for GFRP vinyl-ester pultruded composites at different exposure time, where specimens were conditioning in a hygrothermal chamber operating at 35 °C. Additionally, interlaminar shear test (ILSS) focuses on strength evaluation were performed, as interlaminar is one of the most significantly affected property when composites are exposed to aggressive environments. Finally, a phenomenological model was used to assess the GFRP behavior under conditions applied.

KEYWORDS

Aging, marine environment, interlaminar shear strength.

1. INTRODUCTION

The fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) composites have been expressively used in different sectors due to their excellent physical, chemical and mechanical properties (Agarwal et al., 1981). The FRP composites commonly employed in the oil and gas industry are carbon fiber-reinforced composites (CFRP) and glass fiber-reinforced composites (GFRP) (DANIEL, I. M. e ISHAI, 1994; On et al., 2014). In this scenarios, the composite have several advantages, as simple manufacturing and installation, low production cost and low strength-to-weight ratio (Nguyen et al., 2012; Shamsuddoha et al., 2013), although also present some disadvantages, such as their susceptibility to environmental degradation (i.e., humidity and moderate/high temperature) (Assarar et al., 2011; W. Chen et al., 2016; Ellyin & Maser, 2004; Hu et al., 2014; Kajorncheappunngam et al., 2002; Mourad et al., 2010; Narasimha Murthy et al., 2010; Oguz et al., 2021; Rocha et al., 2017).

The degradation of the mechanical properties of GFRP composites due to exposure to temperatures is primarily attributed to the polymeric matrix and the matrix/fiber interface, with less dependence on the fiber (Alsayed et al., 2012; Correia et al., 2015; Schmidt & d'Almeida, 2018). Heating at a temperature below the glass transition temperature (T_g) does not result in significant property loss (Correia et al., 2015; Safonov et al., 2018). On the other hand, when polymeric composites are exposed to moderate temperatures, i.e., values above the glass transition temperature

(T_g), their stiffness and strength decrease significantly (Alsayed et al., 2012; Bai et al., 2008; Rami Hamad et al., 2017; Vol, 2008; Williann D. Callister, 2012).

Additionally, the degradation of GFRP composite properties in a humid environment is primarily attributed to the sorption (absorption and desorption) of water molecules (Vieira et al., 2023). Moisture penetration in FRPs can occur in the following ways: (i) direct diffusion of water into the polymer matrix through free volumes (Costa et al., 2005; Yang et al., 2020); (ii) capillarity through the fiber/matrix interface of the composite; (iii) transportation through microcracks and voids (Vieira et al., 2023). Generally, moisture absorption primarily leads to the degradation of the matrix dominant properties in polymeric composites, such as interlaminar properties, in-plane shear properties, and transverse tensile properties (Chateauinois et al., 1994; Y. Chen et al., 2007; Costa et al., 2005; Heshmati et al., 2016; Hollaway, 2010; Levine & Slade, 1988; Pomies et al., 1995; Summerscales, 2014; Teixeira de Freitas et al., 2017; Vieira et al., 2023; Yilmaz & Sinmazcelik, 2010). Plasticization (Costa et al., 2005; Levine & Slade, 1988; Summerscales, 2014; Yilmaz & Sinmazcelik, 2010), matrix (or fiber) hydrolysis (Costa et al., 2005; Heshmati et al., 2016; Hollaway, 2010), and matrix swelling (Chateauinois et al., 1994; Y. Chen et al., 2007; Pomies et al., 1995; Teixeira de Freitas et al., 2017) are common phenomena that occurs during aging process, leading to a significant reduction of FRPs properties (Vieira et al., 2023).

In this study, interlaminar shear tests were conducted to investigate the impact of hygrothermal conditioning on the mechanical behavior of pultruded GFRP composites. The failure mechanism and residual properties were also evaluated, with the prediction of property retention using a degradation model.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Materials

The fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) was fabricated using vinylester resin reinforced with glass-fiber. The GFRP materials were provided by manufacturer *Cogumelo*, and were fabricated with pultrusion process. The specimens used alternating layers of unidirectional E-glass reinforcement roving with strand mat (CSM). Figure 1 illustrates the specimens as received. It is important to emphasize that epoxy resin was applied to coat the exposed cut edges, in an attempt to ensure unidirectional diffusion during aging.

Figure 1: GFRP ILSS specimens as-received.

Method

The samples were subjected to hygrothermal aging in a salt-spray chamber operating at a temperature of 35 °C for up to 24 weeks, with constant 95% relative humidity. Groups of samples were periodically removed from the chamber to have their mechanical properties assessed through destructive test. The salt concentration used in the hygrothermal chambers was 5.0% by weight. Additional absorption tests were conducted in specific absorption samples according to ASTM

standards, during the conditioning process, to develop a phenomenological model for evaluating material degradation with aging.

Absorption Test

The absorption test for polymeric composite materials followed the recommendations of ASTM D570 and ASTM D5229/D5229M - 20 [2]. According to ASTM D570 [1], laminated composite samples must be at least 0.13 mm thick, assuming the shape of a rectangle 76.2 mm (3 in.) long and 25.4 mm (1 in.) wide. Four samples were adopted for each aging condition, attending the minimum recommended by ASTM D570 and ASTM D5229/D5229M - 20 [2]. The absorption test measures the mass gain of the samples over time, which is represented by an absorption curve of the average moisture content as a function of time. The moisture content is the ratio between the mass of moisture absorbed by the material and the mass of the dry sample, expressed as a percentage as described in Eq. 1.

$$M, \% = \frac{W_i - W_0}{W_0} \times 100 \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Where W_i is the updated value of the mass of the sample (g) at time i , and W_0 the value of the mass of the sample (g) dry (before conditioning).

Additionally, the unidirectional diffusivity D is obtained by using the slope of the percentage variation of absorbed mass and the square root of time, as shown in Equation 2.

$$D = \pi \left(\frac{h}{4M_\infty} \right)^2 \left(\frac{M_2 - M_1}{\sqrt{t_2} - \sqrt{t_1}} \right)^2 \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Where t represents the conditioning time, M is the absorbed mass, M_∞ is the percentage of absorbed mass at saturation, h is the thickness of the specimen, and the subscripts 1 and 2 represent the initial and final time of the proportionality limit of the curve (initial stage of moisture absorption), respectively.

Interlaminar shear test

The interlaminar shear tests (ILSS) were performed on the unaged and aged specimens aiming to determine the interlaminar shear strength of the composite. These tests were performed in a three-point bending configuration, according to the recommendations of the guidelines of EN ISO 14130 (EN ISO 14130, 1997). A universal tests machine MTS 810.500, with 500kN capacity, with 10 kN load cell were used for the experimental program. The test was conducted under displacement control with a rate of 1 mm/min, up to failure. All the tests were carried out at room temperature (23 ± 2 °C). The geometry of GFRP specimens respected the following proportions: thickness-to-length of 1:10 and thickness to width of 1:5.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Absorption test

The absorption curve of the samples subjected to the salt spray chamber at 35°C is presented in Figure 2 a trend consistent with the literature is observed. The absorbed mass value was 1.7% (± 0.5) after 24 weeks of conditioning, with a diffusion coefficient of 4.9×10^{-6} mm²/s.

Figure 2: Absorption curve after 24 weeks aging.

Interlaminar shear test

Figure 3 presents a box-plot of the strength levels of the aging specimens as a function of time. A box plot shows the middle 50% of the data as a box (interquartile range) and the minimum and maximum values within a certain range as whiskers. The specimens presented a higher loss of strength in early stage of conditioning, which can indicate major degradation at initial stage of absorption. It was also observed a stabilization of strength starting from 4 weeks of aging, indicating water penetration cause similar damage during the experiment. After 24 weeks, the average strength of the samples had sustained levels around 93% of the reference value, which indicates minor degradation of the mechanical properties. Additionally, an increase can be observed in the last aging period. In the case of this study, due to the samples being exposed to 35°C, the influence of temperature is greater at more advanced stage of aging. The phenomenon of post-curing refers to the increased cross-linking bonds, that occurs due to the activation of the points in the polymer chain that are not yet bonded. In a hygrothermal environment, even at moderate temperatures, this phenomenon can occur due to the ease of heat transmission through water molecules penetrated in the samples.

Figure 3: Boxplot of the average strength values after aging.

Additionally, the failure modes were evaluated. The unaged specimens mostly failed by interlaminar shear mode due to delamination in interface of roving and continuous strand mat (CSM) layers. The typical failure modes observed were: (i) interlaminar shear, and rupture occurs due to delamination in one layer, (ii) interlaminar shear, with multiple cracks and rupture occurs due to delamination, (iii) interlaminar shear, with multiple cracks and rupture occurs due to multiple cracking (without complete delamination), (iv) tensile stress, with multiple cracks and rupture

occurs due to tensile stress in the bottom part of the sample, although only case (i) and (ii) happens in references specimens. The cracks are indicated with white arrows in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Failure modes typically observed in the unaged specimens: a) interlaminar shear failure, with delamination of a single layer; b) interlaminar shear failure, with delamination and multiple cracks.

On the other hand, the aged samples showed a mixture of damage mechanisms, as delamination, cracks and plastic deformation, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Example of the failure modes obtained for the aged specimens.

Degradation model

In order to investigate the results obtained from ILSS tests, a phenomenological model previously proposed by Phani and Bose (Phani & Bose, 1987) was used. The model was adapted, where the retention of mechanical properties was used instead of the strength value, as presented in Eq. 3.

$$S = (S_0 - S_\infty)e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} + S_\infty \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

Where S_0 is the initial strength of the unaged material, S_∞ is the strength after infinite time, t is the aging time in hours, and τ is the model's fitting parameter. The model is only valid when the degradation mechanism remains the same throughout the aging process and does not change with temperature.

Figure 6: Adjustment of the Phani and Bose adapted Model (Phani & Bose, 1987) for ILSS results.

The results demonstrate that the retention plateau maintain a retention above 90% according to the models, considering 24 weeks conditioned specimens. The results suggest that exposure to the marine environment for 24 weeks, at least at 35°C, does not seem to affect the interlaminar shear strength retention significantly. This supports the material's resistance to aggressive environment and its suitability to use in structural systems in the offshore industry.

4. CONCLUSION

In summary, the study revealed that the specimens experienced a slight loss of strength during 24 weeks conditioning, suggesting that the material presents a significant aging resistance. However, a consistent decrease occurs after four weeks of aging, from this period onwards, the strength stabilized, indicating that water penetration caused similar damage throughout the experiment. After 24 weeks, the average strength of the samples remained at approximately 93% of the reference value, indicating minor degradation in mechanical properties.

The evaluation of failure modes showed that unaged specimens predominantly failed through interlaminar shear due to delamination at the interface of roving and CSM layers. The observed failure modes included interlaminar shear with and without delamination and tensile stress with multiple cracks. However, only cases interlaminar shear failure occurred in the reference specimens. On the other hand, aged samples exhibited a combination of damage mechanisms, including delamination, cracks, and plastic deformation.

From degradation model, the results demonstrate that the retention maintains 90% of the initial value for specimens conditioned during 24 weeks. Furthermore, the study suggests that exposure to the marine environment for 24 weeks, at least at 35°C, does not appear to significantly affect the retention of interlaminar shear strength.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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